

Start on Sustainability Starter Kit

5. COMMUNITY PARTNERSHIPS

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ABOUT OUR PROJECT

By implementing Start on Sustainability, we aim **to equip micro-enterprises** with the necessary **tools and resources** to take meaningful action towards sustainability, thereby contributing to a more sustainable and resilient EU economy.

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COMMUNITY PARTNERSHIPS

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INTRODUCTION TO THE MODULE

01

OVERVIEW OF THE TOPIC

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OBJECTIVES

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LEARNING OUTCOMES

Community partnerships – what is it?

Community partnerships refer to strategic and sustainable agreements and collaborations between different social sectors such as NGOs, businesses, public institutions, local communities and other stakeholders.

The definition of community partnerships implies that participants in these relationships seek to jointly solve social, economic or environmental problems through collaboration, sharing of resources and knowledge, and coordination of activities. These partnerships aim to strengthen communities, promote sustainable development and build links and trust between different stakeholder groups.

Community partnerships in the context of sustainable development

Community partnerships are a key tool for creating socially responsible and effective initiatives that benefit both local communities and partners from various sectors.

Key elements of the definition of community partnerships include:

- Collaboration and involvement of various community partners.
- Jointly setting goals and action strategies.
- Sharing resources, knowledge and experience.
- Shared responsibility for achieving results and monitoring progress.
- Building lasting relationships based on trust and mutual understanding.

Origins of the definition of "community partnership"

The beginnings of community partnerships can be traced to the development of the CSR concept in the second half of the 20th century. At that time, companies began to recognise their role not only towards shareholders, but also towards local communities, employees, customers and other stakeholders. Partnerships with communities became a tool for implementing CSR through engagement with society and the environment.

With the development of the idea of sustainable development in the 1980s and 1990s, growing environmental and social awareness posed new challenges for companies. Partnerships with local communities began to be seen as a key element of harmonious economic, social and environmental development.

OBJECTIVES

In this module of our study, you will learn why building a community partnership is important for sustainable development.

Below, we will outline the main objectives and importance of such partnerships for businesses.

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**SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS
OPERATIONS**

01

Understanding of local needs and challenges

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Trust building

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Supporting the development of local communities

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Co-creation of social values

Understanding of local needs and challenges

Understanding local community needs and challenges is a key element in building effective community partnerships in the context of sustainable development.

Main rule:

- Organising regular meetings
- Effective data analysis, including demographic and economic data
- Cooperation with local leaders
- Presence in the media and social media.

Trust building

In order for your company to inspire social trust, it is worth focusing on:

- Transparent and active communication,
- Formulating a clear company goal,
- Building lasting relationships,
- Effectiveness of actions,
- Ensuring employee well-being and maintain partnership relations.

Building trust within community partnerships is a process that requires patience, consistency and authenticity. However, effective cooperation based on trust can bring many benefits for both the company and the local community.

Supporting the development of local communities

What is important, what aspect should be taken care of?

- Maintain an inclusive work environment,
- Take care of your employees, offer access to development, training, courses,
- Get involved in projects in the field of ecology and environmental protection,
- Support local schools and universities,
- Take part in charity events.

Shared responsibility for the environment

The idea of shared environmental responsibility refers to the need for companies to engage in environmental action in partnership with others, including other companies, local communities, NGOs, governments and consumers.

- Establish cooperation with other companies,
- Cooperates with non-governmental organisations,
- Create ecological awareness among employees and externally,
- Choose ecological products.

Create innovative solutions

Ways to formulate creative and effective methods that promote engagement, cooperation and mutual support in the local community. What could it be?

- **Digital or e-learning platforms:** mobile platforms that facilitate online interaction and personal development, offering a variety of educational resources.
- **Artistic and cultural programs:** initiatives such as art workshops, local culture festivals and street murals that celebrate and promote community engagement in the arts.
- **Ecological activities:** Creating projects and activities related to environmental protection. E.g. ecological competitions.
- **Health and sports programs:** Creating health programs that promote physical activity, healthy eating habits and mental health. e.g. **well-being in the workplace** as a company goal.

Co-creation of social values

Social cooperation contributes to the creation of social values that not only generate economic benefits but, above all, protect the natural environment.

How can you co-create social impact initiatives with your customers to promote sustainability?

- You need to know your customers based on their characteristics, behaviors, preferences.
- The basis of the value co-creation process is to generate benefits both for your company and customers, as well as for society and the environment. You can co-create value by engaging your customers,
- To ensure that your co-creation initiatives are effective, you need to measure their impact on sustainable development outcomes, customer satisfaction, and social and environmental results. Use indicators and metrics that are relevant, specific, measurable, achievable, realistic, and timely to evaluate your impact.

What to do to create a community partnership in your company?

1. Maintaining positive relationships with stakeholders,
2. Supporting clusters and clubs operating locally,
3. Increasing employee involvement in local communities,
4. Taking care of local sustainable development,
5. Using the services of local suppliers,
6. Enhancing external visibility to improve the image - effective marketing.

Step-by-step process to create community partnerships

1. Analysis of local needs and development opportunities
2. Identification and good relations with non-governmental organisations, local authorities and universities.
3. Developing goals
4. Actively establishing contacts
5. Organisation of meetings, events or training
6. Creating or participating in industry interest groups, e.g. clusters
7. Maintaining good communication – with everyone! Respond to emails, phone calls, and be open.

Why are community partnerships meaningful?

Creating community partnerships within a company is crucial, especially in the context of building a sustainable economy.

- **Boosting employee morale:** Actions taken together for a common goal can significantly boost employee morale. When employees feel that their company engages in good social activities, they feel greater job satisfaction, which in turn can lead to increased employee retention.

- **Work life balance:** A new look at work values. Younger generations make decisions about work not only based on salary. Work-life balance is important to them.
- **Team building:** Organising volunteering events builds a sense of community and teamwork.
- **Get the word out:** Launching a public relations campaign to tell people about your company's charitable work, will not only project your company in a positive light, but it will also raise awareness about the charities you support.

Groups interested in community development and social causes

- **Women's Clubs:** Groups focusing on supporting and empowering women in the workplace,
- **Thematic Clusters:** Specialised groups bringing together employees interested in specific topics, e.g. a construction cluster,
- **Book Clubs:** Reading groups that organise meetings to discuss books,
- **Fitness Clubs:** Groups dedicated to promoting healthy lifestyles by organising joint workouts, sports events.
- **Volunteer groups.** Social activities.

“Coming together is a beginning; keeping together is progress; working together is success.”

Henry Ford

03

CASE STUDIES

01

Case study 1: Starbucks

02

Case study 2: Allegro

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Case study 3: H&M

Starbucks

Starbucks has a long history of community engagement and partnerships with local communities. Some of their notable activities are:

- Sustainable coffee cultivation, which supports local coffee producers and protects the environment,
- Youth training programmes, charity events.
- In 2020, the brand has collaborated with EcoBean, a startup and is supporting it in its work on the possibilities offered by grounds processing - mainly by donating the waste collected in Warsaw cafés for tests on the reuse of the raw material. This aligns with most of the cafe's guests who live the idea of zero waste on a daily basis.

Starbucks

- Availability of the brand's products in the "Too Good To Go" application, whose mission is to reduce food waste.
- Since the beginning of its operations in Poland, Starbucks has been developing the "Bring Your Own Tumbler" initiative, which aims to reduce waste production and educate society. The "With your own cup" concept was created keeping the environment in mind and spreading good practices among guests,
- Cooperation with PSONI, i.e. the Polish Association for People with Intellectual Disabilities.
- The brand also decided to support one of the Finales' of the Wielka Orkiestra Świątecznej Pomocy.

Allegro

“Sustainable development and social activity are embedded in Allegro's DNA, and responsibility for our customers, sellers, employees and care for the environment are our most important obligations.”

The overriding commitment for all areas of activity is to act ethically and with full transparency:

- Providing a creative and innovative workplace,
- Taking care of our customers,
- Responsible cooperation in business ,
- Investment in the community,
- Creating a healthy and green attitude.

Allegro

Examples of Allegro activities:

- Allegro Lokalnie: Local community support. Allegro Lokalnie are mainly private individuals who most often offer single copies of a given product.
- Allegro engages in charitable activities by supporting various non-governmental organisations and foundations.
- Recycling packaging or promoting ecological products on the platform.
- The company supports various cultural and artistic initiatives by organising events promoting local artists and creators.

H&M

Another example of a European clothing company engaging in social activities and sustainable development is H&M. H&M is an international clothing retailer known for its efforts to promote responsible fashion and social involvement.

- Use of organic materials, recycling of fabrics or reduction of water and energy consumption in the production process.
- Support for local production communities in the countries where H&M garments are produced.
- H&M works to address poverty and support local communities through charitable initiatives and partnerships with non-profit organisations.

“In teamwork, silence isn’t golden. It’s deadly.”

Mark Sanborn

04

ASSESSMENT

Q1

The origins of Community Partnerships are linked to the emergence of:

- A. CSR Concept
- B. ESG Concept
- C. It is a relatively new concept and it is not linked to any of the above

Q2

Key elements in building effective community partnerships are:

- A. Approaching your partnerships as a resident “expert”
- B. Assuming an immediate partnership
- C. Understanding local community needs & challenges

Q3

Why community partnership in the company is important?

- A. Brings immediate profit for the company
- B. Helps strengthen leadership positions in the company
- C. Improves employees morale

Q4

Examples of socially active groups in the company can be:

- A. Trade unions
- B. Women's clubs
- C. Recruitment agencies

Answer Key

Q1: A

Q2: C

Q3: C

Q4: B

05

KEY TERMS AND DEFINITIONS

-
1. Social Impact Assessment
 2. Volunteering
 3. Co-creation of Value
 4. Community Partnership
 5. Social marketing
 6. Social Enterprise

06

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REFERENCES

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Thank You
Any questions?

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